

3D-Printed PLA/PEO Blend as Biodegradable Substrate Coating with CoCl₂ for Colorimetric Humidity Detection

Nattanicha Chaiya^{a,b,c}, Donraporn Daranarong^d, Patnarin Worajittiphon^{a,b}, Runglawan Somsunan^a, Puttinan Meepowpan^{a,b}, Adisorn Tuantranont^e, Nawasit Rakbamrung^f, Paul D. Topham^g, Brian J. Tighe^g, Anisa Mahomed^g and Winita Punyodom^{a,b,h}

^{a)} Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Chiang Mai University, Chiang Mai 50200, Thailand

^{b)} Department of Chemistry and Center for Innovation in Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Chiang Mai University, Chiang Mai 50200, Thailand

^{c)} Graduate School, Chiang Mai University, Chiang Mai 50200, Thailand

^{d)} Science and Technology Research Institute, Chiang Mai University, Chiang Mai 50200, Thailand

^{e)} National Security and Dual-Use Technology Center, National/Science and Technology Development Agency, Pathumthani 12120, Thailand

^{f)} Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Burapha University, Chon Buri, 20131, Thailand

^{g)} Aston Institute of Materials Research, College of Engineering and Physical Sciences, Aston University, Birmingham, United Kingdom

^{h)} Center of Excellence in Materials Science and Technology, Chiang Mai University, Chiang Mai 50200, Thailand

*Corresponding Author's E-mail: winitacmu@gmail.com

Abstract

This study aimed to fabricate biodegradable substrate with colorimetric humidity indicator for detective moisture in food packaging. The poor properties of poly(lactic acid) (PLA) were enhanced by melt blending PLA with non-toxic poly(ethylene oxide) PEO at 180 °C.

30 Specifically, three-dimensional (3D) substrates of PLA/PEO blends were fabricated by solvent-
31 cast 3D printing. Furthermore, cobalt chloride (CoCl₂) solution was printed onto the substrate
32 with an inkjet printer to serve as a colorimetric humidity sensing indicator. It found that the
33 flexibility and thermal stability of the PLA were improved and the hydrophilicity was increased
34 with an increase in PEO content. Color changes and the sensitivity of this material were
35 confirmed using image analysis and total color difference. The CoCl₂ indicator displayed color
36 changes that ranged from blue to pink under ambient conditions (above 60%RH), revealing
37 suitable potential for frozen food packaging material with aim to detect amount of moisture in the
38 packaging.

39

40 **Keywords:** Poly(lactic acid): Poly(ethylene oxide): Polymer blend: Colorimetric humidity
41 sensor: 3D printing: Inkjet printing

42

43 1. Introduction

44 The development of biodegradable polymers for smart packaging to produce more
45 environmentally friendly materials, such as poly(lactic acid) (PLA), has generated significant
46 interest because of its biodegradability, non-toxicity, renewability, and compostability
47 [Drumright, Gruber, & Henton, 2000]. PLA is a bioplastic that is derived from renewable
48 agricultural resources and is being used in the food industry to package products or biomedical
49 materials. However, the limitations of PLA and its applications are attributed to the brittleness of
50 PLA as a substrate, as well as its poor thermal stability and hydrophobicity. Thus, its effective
51 use in many applications has been limited [Auras, Harte, & Selke, 2004]. As a way of responding
52 to the problems mentioned above, there has been greater interest and attention paid to mixing
53 other biocompatible polymers with PLA by copolymerization [Phetsuk *et al.*, 2020;
54 Ruengdechawiwat *et al.*, 2016] or blending [Suthapakti *et al.*, 2017; Tuancharoensri, Ross,
55 Mahasaranon, Topham, & S. Ross, 2017] in order to enhance the limitations of PLA.

56 Most research studies have blended polymers by way of solution blending methods that do
57 not employ high-heat temperatures. This was done to avoid the degradation of polymers through
58 the use of lower thermal degradation temperatures (T_d). Before the fabrication step, the melt-
59 blending technique was performed to blend polymers without the need for solvents. This
60 technique involved heating temperatures that were above the melting temperature of the polymers
61 in order to achieve a homogeneous polymeric material [Arias, Heuzey, Huneault, Ausias, &
62 Bendahou, 2014].

63 To improve the thermal properties, impact strength and hydrophilicity of PLA, it has been
64 widely copolymerized or blended with various polymers to improve some of its advantageous
65 properties. These polymers include natural rubber [Oyama, 2009; Ruengdechawiwat *et al.*, 2016],
66 poly(n-butyl acrylate) [Tachaphiboonsap & Jarukumjorn, 2003], poly(butylene succinate) [Lalita
67 *et al.*, 2013], polycaprolactone (PCL) [Hoidy, Al-Mulla, & Al-Janabi, 2010; Jompang *et al.*,
68 2013], poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) [Li, Liang, Zhang, & Zhu, 2015; Sheth, Kumar, Davé, Gross,
69 & Mccarthy, 1997] or poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) [Eom, Choi, & Park, 2019; Nijenhuis,
70 Colstee, Grijpma, & Pennings, 1996; Oliveira *et al.*, 2013; Saha, Samal, Biswal, Mohanty, &
71 Nayak, 2018]. Several researchers have reported on the establishment of improved properties of

72 the PLA composites by adding PEG into the PLA matrix [Anderson & Hillmyer, 2004].
73 Remarkably, the addition of PEG content in PLA increased its ductility, thermal properties and
74 mechanical properties [Li *et al.*, 2015]. In addition, the biodegradation rate of PLA was also
75 increased [Pasut *et al.*, 2016]. The main function of PEG is as a polymeric plasticizer in the
76 structure of the polymer chain [Gajria, Davé, Gross, & McCarthy, 1996]. According to Bailey *et al.*,
77 when the molecular weight of PEG exceeds 100,000 g/mol, it is named PEO [Bailey,
78 Koleske, & Frederick, 1976]. PEO is a water soluble, nontoxic polymer with strong hydrophilic
79 properties. Yoojun *et al.* focused on melt-blended PLA in different amounts of PEO and several
80 researches also reported that the addition of PEO into PLA increased the flexibility, Izod impact
81 strength and hydrophilicity of the PLA [Eom *et al.*, 2019; Nijenhuis *et al.*, 1996; Oliveira *et al.*,
82 2013]. Through its effective application, humidity sensors using PEO electrospun fibre have been
83 studied [Chen & Lu, 2005]. Under higher 87%RH, the opaque PEO electrospun fibre mesh
84 became more transparent and began to fuse together. As mentioned above, PEO could be used for
85 humidity monitoring with the naked eye, wherein low toxicity and irreversibility values can be
86 determined. This opens up the opportunity to manipulate our environmentally friendly systems
87 and use them as humidity sensors to demonstrate the broad applicability of this materials design
88 approach.

89 Humidity sensors are a fast and reliable way of identifying when products have been
90 exposed to a high humidity. Several different types of humidity sensors have been studied. Each
91 of these sensors are based on a different principle. Some of the different sensors include
92 capacitive, resistive, gravimetric and optical types [Gu, Huang, & Qin, 2004; Tian *et al.*, 2008;
93 Tsigara *et al.*, 2007; Yu *et al.*, 2006; Yu, Xy, Lee, & Li, 2013]. According to the relative
94 humidity values (RH), humidity sensors can be classified into three types; a ceramic sensing
95 material that uses porous materials to detect humidity, a semiconducting sensing material that
96 uses a semiconductor and a polymer-based humidity sensor that uses semi-conductive properties
97 to detect humidity. In previous research, polymer-based humidity sensors were investigated by
98 measuring their response to humidity levels through changes in conductivity [Wang, Fu, Duan, &
99 Li, 2015]. Two typical polyelectrolytes, poly(dimethyldiallylammonium chloride) and
100 poly(sodium *p*-styrene sulfonate), were used for humidity detection. However, they are known to
101 be non-biodegradable polymers. To easily detect humidity with the naked eye, color changes are
102 observed in humidity sensors when several intermediate agents have been applied including
103 photonic crystals [Hawkeye & Brett, 2011; Tian *et al.*, 2008], polymer electrolyte thin films
104 [Kim, Kim, Jo, Kim, & Park, 2012] and crystalline covalent organic framework nanofibers
105 [Huang *et al.*, 2013]. Furthermore, the most commonly known additives that are used as
106 colorimetric humidity indicators, such as silica gel or cobalt(II) chloride [You *et al.*, 2017], are
107 currently being used in commercial applications. This work aimed to fabricate melt-blended
108 PLA/PEO as the primary biodegradable substrate of humidity sensors and to coat a colorimetric
109 humidity indicator onto the substrate by way of new printing technology. A humidity detector
110 employing a polyester, such as PLA, will be fabricated. The detector will be safe for the
111 environment because of its non-toxic biodegradable components.

112 In general, a simple technique of layer-by-layer (LbL) coating was used in the immersion
113 (dip-coating) step when the substrate was immersed into the solution. However, this technique

114 commonly results in the production of chemical waste and is considered a time-consuming
115 process that involves a series of dipping cycles [Akagi, Fujiwara, & Akashi, 2012]. With regard
116 to current fabrication technology, three-dimensional (3D) and inkjet printing are now being
117 widely used. These technologies offer several advantages when compared to other common
118 methods. The advantages include the deposition of thin films that are considered both time-
119 efficient and cost-effective because there is no need for an intermediate rinsing step [Akagi *et al.*,
120 2012]. The process has also been easily automated as it involves high speeds and accomplishes
121 room temperature deposition through easy control patterns and minimal thicknesses of the
122 deposited material [Mensing, Wisitsoraat, Tuantranont, & Kerdcharoen, 2013]. In printed PLA
123 studies, Guo and co-workers successfully fabricated the solvent-cast printing of a 3D
124 microstructure from polylactide inks through the use of 3D printing [Guo, Heuzey, & Therriault,
125 2014]. The multifunctional microsystem of the PLA solutions by solvent-cast 3D printing was
126 thoroughly investigated [Guo *et al.*, 2013]. These novel 3D microstructure fabrications tend to
127 use PLA solutions in various applications including tissue engineering scaffolds, stimuli-
128 responsive materials and microelectronic devices [Guo *et al.*, 2014]. However, these technologies
129 have rarely been investigated with regard to the LbL fabrication of the colorimetric humidity
130 indicator solution onto a polymer substrate.

131 In this work, a PLA biodegradable polymer blended with a non-toxic PEO polymer as
132 environmental friendly materials to create a main humidity label substrate was investigated. A
133 convenient, fast and various designs of 3D printing technique are interesting to design and control
134 the PLA/PEO blends to fabricate a novel biodegradable substrate of humidity sensor for the first
135 time. Moreover, a fast and continuous process of inkjet printing technique is interesting to coat
136 CoCl_2 as a commercial colorimetric humidity indicator in a non-toxic amount to environmental
137 and clearly seen a change in color. Therefore, PLA/PEO blends, the biodegradable and non-toxic
138 materials can be fabricated to manipulate our environmental friendly system as an eco-friendly
139 colorimetric humidity detective label.

141 2. Experimental

142 2.1 Raw materials

143 The poly(lactic acid) (PLA) resin used in this study was obtained from Bioplastic
144 Production Laboratory for Medical Applications, Thailand, while the poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO)
145 powder was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, USA. The glass transition temperature (T_g) and
146 melting temperature (T_m) of the PLA were 61 and 179°C, respectively. PEO with a weight-
147 average molecular weight (\bar{M}_w) of 100,000-200,000 and a melting temperature (T_m) of 68°C was
148 blended with PLA. Cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate ($\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was obtained from QRëC,
149 New Zealand. Chloroform (CHCl_3) and formic acid ($\geq 98\%$) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich,
150 Germany. Dimethylformamide (DMF) (Fisher, England) was used as the solvent for $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$
151 dissolution. All of the solvents were of analytical grade and were used without any further
152 purification.

156 **2.2 Preparation of PLA/PEO blends by melt-blending technique**

157 The 3:1 PLA/PEO melt-blends were prepared from 5 %w/v polymer blends. The PLA
158 pellets and PEO powder were mixed together before being melt-blended in an internal mixer
159 (HAAKE™ Rheomix OS Lab Mixers). The mixtures were melt-blended for 8 minutes at 180 °C
160 using a screw rotational speed of 130 rpm [Lalita et al., 2013]. A yellow homogenous compound
161 was obtained and ground into pellets for use as feeding material in the 3D printing process.

162

163 **2.3 3D Printing of PLA/PEO blends**

164 Solvent-cast printing was performed to fabricate the 3D polymer substrate at ambient
165 temperatures using a 3D printer (3D-bioplotter® EnvisionTEC). In order to study the 3D
166 structure of the PLA/PEO blends for use as a substrate, a 3:1 ratio of the PLA/PEO blends
167 obtained from the internal mixer was dissolved in the CHCl₃ solvent at concentrations of 20, 30
168 and 40 %w/v. Subsequently, various concentrations of the polymer solutions were allowed to rest
169 in sealed bottom containers for 24 h at room temperature. After 24 h, the solutions were stirred
170 and sonicated to obtain homogeneous polymer solutions before the 3D fabrication processing.
171 Importantly, the viscosity of the polymer solution should be less than 1.0 dL/g. The polymer
172 solutions were then loaded into a low-temperature cartridge at 25 °C.

173 The applied pressure and printing speeds were within the range of 3-4.5 bars and 25-30
174 mm/s, respectively, while all gauge sizes were also studied. The “VisualMachine” computer
175 program was used to control the printing process and “Solid works” was used to design a layer-
176 by-layer 3D structure to determine the desired size, shape and thickness.

177

178 **2.4 Fabrication of colorimetric humidity sensors by inkjet printing**

179 Cobalt chloride solution was used as the ink for inkjet printing. The ink was prepared by
180 dissolved CoCl₂•6H₂O in dimethylformamide (DMF) and was filtered (through a pore size of less
181 than 0.30 μm) and loaded into a cartridge before the fabrication process. A commercial inkjet
182 material printer, Fujifilm Dimatrix DMP 2800 piezoelectric inkjet printer, was used to print the
183 ink onto the 3D substrate without an intermediate rinsing step. The “Drop Manager” computer
184 program was used to control the printing process with 20 jetting nozzles and 32V firing voltage.
185 The printing process was repeated by applying 4 cycles of the ink on the 3D substrate over a
186 square-shaped area of 4 cm × 4 cm. The processing time per cycle was about 180 s.

187

188 **2.5 Measurements**

189 **2.5.1 PLA-based substrate improvement**

190 Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopic analysis was performed with a
191 wavenumber range between 600-3200 cm⁻¹. Differential scanning calorimeter (DSC, Perkin-
192 Elmer DSC7) was used to determine the thermal properties of the various substrates with a
193 heating rate of 10 °C/min from 0 to 220 °C. The weight loss value and degradation temperature
194 were determined using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, Perkin-Elmer TGA7) at 20 °C/min
195 from 50 to 550 °C in a nitrogen atmosphere. Tensile tests were performed using a universal
196 testing machine (Lloyds LRX+ Universal Mechanical Testing Machine) to determine the tensile
197 strength and elongation at break with a loading cell of 10 N. The tensile speed was 10 mm/min

198 and a 50 mm gauge length was used. A dimension of each test specimen was 70 mm × 10 mm
199 (length × width) with a thickness of ~0.1 mm. All samples were tested 5 times and the average
200 values were reported. The surface morphology was observed using a scanning electron
201 microscope (SEM, JEOL 5910 LV), while energy dispersive x-ray analysis (EDX, JEOL 5910
202 LV) was used to identify the elemental composition on the substrate. The degree of surface
203 wettability was then evaluated by water contact angle measurement.

204

205 **2.5.2 PLA-based humidity sensor for color observation**

206 To determine humidity measurements, saturated salt solutions were used in closed
207 containers that contained saturated lithium chloride (~12% RH), saturated magnesium chloride
208 (~33% RH), saturated magnesium nitrate (~52% RH), saturated copper(II) chloride (~68),
209 saturated sodium chloride (~75%RH) and water (~100% RH) in order to establish humidity
210 control. To observe changes in colors, photographs of the samples were taken with a digital
211 camera (Canon EOS1100D). The RGB of the images [Bridgeman, Corral, Quach, Xian, &
212 Forzani, 2014] were analyzed with the use of the “Photoshop” computer program. Colorimeter
213 (MINOLTA CR-400) was then used to determine the total color difference (TCD) using the
214 following equation [Díaz, Candia, & Cobos, 2016; Díaz, Ferreiro, Rodríguez-Otero, & Cobos,
215 2019]:

216

$$217 \quad TCD = [(\Delta L^*)^2 + (\Delta a^*)^2 + (\Delta b^*)^2]^{1/2} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

218

219 where ΔL^* , Δa^* and Δb^* are representative of the differentials of lightness, green and
220 yellow between the samples and the initial labels, respectively.

221

222 **3. Results and discussion**

223 **3.1 Property improvement of PLA/PEO blends**

224 **3.1.1 FTIR spectroscopy**

225 Among various spectroscopic techniques, FTIR spectroscopy is commonly used in
226 analyzing the interaction between PLA and PEO. Both spectral band width and intensity may be
227 correlated with the strength and extent of hydrogen bonding [Oliveira *et al.*, 2013]. Two
228 completely incompatible polymers show no spectral interaction, whereas compatible polymers
229 that do have chemical interactions reflect such changes in the IR spectrum in the form of band
230 shifts, band widening and changes in band intensity [Oliveira *et al.*, 2013].

231 The IR spectra (600–3200 cm^{-1} region) of the PLA/PEO mixtures were consistent with
232 chemical interactions between PLA and PEO (Figure 1). In the spectrum of the 3:1 PLA/PEO
233 blend, all the featured FTIR absorption peaks of PLA and PEO were almost similar. This would
234 indicate the non-existence of any chemical interactions within the blended films. Additionally, no
235 new bands were formed or strong chemical interactions occurred with the polymer blends. From
236 Table 1, a decrease in C—O—C (carbonyl) stretching can be seen in regards to the CH₃
237 stretching vibration for the 3:1 PLA/PEO blend in comparison with PLA. This was determined to
238 be a consequence of the redistribution of the helical structure of PLA. This revealed that the α
239 crystal structure of the PLA has been partially converted into the β crystal structure due to a

240 change in its helical conformation during crystallization, thus indicating the effect of PEO as a β
 241 nucleating agent [Saha *et al.*, 2018].
 242

243
 244 **Figure 1.** FTIR spectra of neat PLA, 3:1 PLA/PEO blend and neat PEO (left) and focus in 900-
 245 2000 cm^{-1} range (right).
 246

247 **Table 1.** FTIR ratio of the neat PLA, 3:1 PLA/PEO blend and the neat PEO.

Assignment	Wavenumber (cm^{-1})	FTIR ratio		
		Neat PLA	3:1 PLA/PEO blend	Neat PEO
COC/CH ₃	1087/1460	0.8	0.3	-
C=O/CO	1760/1107	-	0.9	-

248
 249 **3.1.2 Thermal properties tests**
 250 The DSC thermogram was carried out to analyze the thermal properties *via* the second
 251 heating run. The thermal properties included the glass transition temperature (T_g), crystallization
 252 temperature (T_c), melting temperature (T_m), and the decomposition temperatures (T_d) which are
 253 all presented in Table 2. The T_m of the neat PLA and PEO values were 178.8 and 67.7 $^{\circ}\text{C}$,
 254 respectively and indicated that polymers are the semicrystalline. The T_m of the PLA/PEO blends
 255 derived from both PLA and PEO were recorded at 171.7 and 54.2 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively. The results
 256 indicated compatibility of the PLA/PEO blends when the blends are mixed using an internal
 257 mixer. Blending PLA with PEO also slightly reduced the T_g , T_c and T_m values when compared
 258 with PLA. Similar results were reported by Sara *et al.* and Yoojun *et al.* also found that the
 259 addition of PEO content into PLA decreased the T_g , T_c , and T_m values [Eom *et al.*, 2019; Oliveira
 260 *et al.*, 2013; Saha *et al.*, 2018]. A decrease in T_g indicated that PEO could enhance the chain
 261 mobility of PLA. Moreover, a decrease in the T_c value from 120.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 115.0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, when PEO was
 262 added into the PLA, indicated that PLA crystallized at lower temperatures. This was due to the

263 fact that PEO accelerated the crystallinity of the blends. In addition, PEO was found to be good
 264 for the mobility of the molecular chain due to a plasticizing effect of PEO on the PLA matrix
 265 [Eom *et al.*, 2019; Li, Zhang, Liang, & Wang, 2015; Park, Song, Park, & Yoon, 2011].
 266 Furthermore, it was deemed beneficial as it increased its flexibility which is desirable when it is
 267 used as a substrate.

268 In order to investigate thermal stability, thermalgravimetric analysis was performed on the
 269 neat PLA, neat PEO and the 3:1 PLA/PEO blend. The thermal degradation behavior of the
 270 relative weight loss as a function of temperature was determined from the thermalgravimetric
 271 curves. The TGA thermograms exhibited important weight loss over the temperature range. An
 272 increase in the T_d value of the PLA/PEO blends indicated that the temperature at 95% weight loss
 273 increased from 390.6 (neat PLA) to 405.2 (3:1 PLA/PEO blends). Furthermore, the temperature
 274 increased to 435.8 °C when compared to that of the neat PEO. Moreover, in agreement with
 275 Yoojun *et al.*, the addition of PEO content in PLA gradually increased the thermal stability of the
 276 PLA [Eom *et al.*, 2019]. The main thermal characteristic data of the neat PLA, neat PEO and the
 277 3:1 PLA/PEO blends are presented in Table 2. Remarkably, the 3:1 PLA/PEO blends displayed
 278 better thermal stability than the neat PLA.

279

280 **Table 2.** Thermal properties of PLA, PEO and PLA/PEO blend.

	T_g (°C)	T_m (°C)	T_c (°C)	T_d (°C)	ΔH_{cc} (J/g)	ΔH_m (J/g)
Neat PLA	60.8	178.8	120.5	390.6	32.7	45.0
PLA/PEO blend	54.8	171.7	115.0	405.2	35.5	40.6
Neat PEO	-	67.7	-	435.8	-	103.3

281

282 3.1.3 Mechanical properties test

283 The mechanical properties of the neat PLA and 3:1 PLA/PEO blended films, such as tensile
 284 strength (MPa) and elongation at the break (%), were studied and the results are presented in
 285 Table 3 and Figure 2. Figure 2 displays comparisons of the mechanical properties between neat
 286 PLA and PLA/PEO blends. Ultimate strength and elongation values at the break of neat PLA
 287 film, as shown in Figure 2(a), were 26.4 MPa and 3.4%, respectively. The ultimate strength,
 288 modulus and elongation at break of the 3:1 of PLA/PEO blended film moderately decreased from
 289 26.4 to 13.0 MPa, 1333.0 to 266.4 MPa and increased from 3.4 to 8.1%, respectively when
 290 compared with the neat PLA film. The results indicate a decrease in ultimate strength and
 291 modulus of the neat PLA film along with the addition of PEO content, whereas the elongation at
 292 break of the PLA/PEO blended film increased by twice as much as the neat PLA film. A
 293 significant decrease in the ultimate strength and modulus, as well as a two-fold increase in the
 294 elongation at the break, was caused by PLA plasticizing with PEO. Similar studies on the
 295 mechanical properties of the PLA and PLA/PEO blended films have been reported [Eom *et al.*,
 296 2019; Nijenhuis *et al.*, 1996; Saha *et al.*, 2018]. It has been further reported that the addition of 5
 297 wt% PEO in the PLA caused a decrease in the ultimate strength of the PLA/PEO blended film,
 298 while the elongation at the break increased due to the plasticizing effect of PEO [Nijenhuis *et al.*,
 299 1996]. Sara *et al.* reported that by adding PEO content by over 4 wt%, a sharp decrease in tensile
 300 strength occurred. This outcome is related to the phase separation of PEO over 4 wt% in the PLA

301 matrix. In addition, a decrease in tensile strength and an increase in elongation at break are
 302 consequences of the increasingly rubbery nature of PLA when it is mixed with PEO. Therefore,
 303 the presence of PEO content could improve the mechanical properties of PLA as a result of the
 304 plasticizer property within the structure of PEO.
 305

306
 307 **Figure 2.** Mechanical properties of neat PLA film and 3:1 PLA/PEO blended film: (a) Stress-
 308 strain curves and (b) Mechanical properties comparison.
 309

310 **Table 3.** Tensile properties of PLA and PLA/PEO blended films.

Sample	Ultimate Strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)	Young's modulus (MPa)
Neat PLA film	26.4 ± 2.2	3.4	1333.0 ± 184.4
Polymer blends film	13.0 ± 0.7	8.1	266.4 ± 25.2

311

312 3.1.4 Water contact angle

313 A suitable substrate should easily absorb water for the surface coating process. To compare
 314 the surface wettability of various substrates, the water contact angle is used to indicate the
 315 hydrophilicity of the substrate. As is evident from Table 4, the water contact angle of the neat
 316 PLA film and the 3:1 PLA/PEO blended film were 71.19° and 48.07° , respectively. When PEO
 317 content was added to the PLA, the water contact angle decreased due to an increase in the
 318 hydroxyl groups (-OH) of PEO in the PLA structure. In nature, PEO is more hydrophilic and is a
 319 polymeric amphiphile that contains a nonpolar hydrophobic region (ethylene unit) and a polar
 320 hydrophilic region (ether oxygen) in the polymer chain [Bailey *et al.*, 1976]. Moreover, the
 321 plasticizing effect of PEO encouraged the diffusion of water molecules through chain mobility
 322 [Nijenhuis *et al.*, 1996]. A similar study conducted by Juliano *et al.* determined that the contact
 323 angle for various PEO concentrations added to the PLA indicated that the contact angle for all the
 324 blended samples (1:0, 1:3, 1:1, 3:1, and 0:1 PLA/PEO ratios) was within the ranges of the neat
 325 PLA (120°) and the neat PEO (38°).

326 Furthermore, no significant differences were observed between the 3:1 PLA/PEO blended
 327 film and the 3D substrate of 3:1 PLA/PEO blends. The smooth surface of the blended films
 328 resulted in lower contact angles compared to the rough surface of the 3D blended substrate. The
 329 3:1 PLA/PEO blend had the lowest contact angle and the results indicate that some of the PEO
 330 was exposed on the surface in each of the blends. When the surface came in contact with a water
 331 droplet, the PEO fraction on the surface absorbed the water droplet. As a result, PEO enhances
 332 the hydrophilicity of PLA and this is useful in the process of coating the substrate.
 333

334 **Table 4.** Water contact angle analysis of neat PLA film, 3:1 PLA/PEO blended film and 3D
 335 substrate of PLA/PEO blend.

Sample	Water contact angle (°)	
Neat PLA film		71.2 ± 0.4
Polymer blends film		48.1 ± 2.4
3D of Polymer blends		55.7 ± 0.6

336

337 3.1.5 Surface morphology

338 The surface morphology of various substrates was studied with the use of a scanning
 339 electron microscope (SEM) and a light microscope. The SEM images of the neat PLA film, the
 340 polymer blended film and the 3D substrate of the polymer blends are shown in Figure 3. For the
 341 surface analysis, the neat PLA film (Figure 3(a)) had a smooth surface and was not found to be
 342 porous. Thus, it displayed poor ability to hold and absorb both water and ink. While adding PEO
 343 content to PLA, the substrate of the 3:1 ratio of the PLA/PEO blended film (Figure 3(b)) was
 344 more porous and the unequal size of the pores allowed water or ink to spread throughout the film.
 345 This porous microstructure of the 3:1 PLA/PEO blended substrate resulted in an inferior barrier
 346 property, forming diffusion pathways for oxygen and water vapor [Saha *et al.*, 2018].
 347 Consequently, the water absorption of the polymer blended film was found to be better than the
 348 neat PLA film due to its porous surface and the hydroxyl groups of the PEO structure. Figures
 349 3(c)-(d) present microscopic images that clearly show the substrate coated with CoCl₂ were blue,
 350 while prior to coating the substrate appears to be white. This occurs because of the presence of a
 351 larger number of cavities and thus surface area. This was due to both the design and the
 352 fabrication technique that was used. Thus, the substrate was able to absorb both water and ink,
 353 which ultimately increased the number of opportunities for interactions with its surroundings.

354 Post coating the surface with CoCl_2 solution by inkjet printing, EDX was used to identify
355 the elemental composition on the surface. EDX spectrums are displayed as insets in Figures 3(e)-
356 (f). The elements on the surface included Co, Cl, O and C, as shown in Table 5. Therefore, the
357 EDX results confirmed that the 3D substrate of the 3:1 blend of PLA/PEO could be successfully
358 coated with cobalt chloride solution with the use of inkjet printing technology.

359 In this research, the PLA biodegradable polymer was blended with biodegradable
360 counterparts, such as PEO non-toxic polymers, to develop a safe substrate for environmentally
361 friendly materials and to also retain the biodegradability of PLA. Moreover, the CoCl_2 solution as
362 a humidity indicator coated the 3D substrate via inkjet printing technology in small picolitres in
363 order to be conscious of certain potential environmental problems.

364 According to findings of the previous studies mentioned above, the 3:1 PLA/PEO blend has
365 optimal ratios of PLA and PEO blending for use in fabricating a 3D substrate of colorimetric
366 humidity sensors. With regards to the thermal properties, DSC confirmed that the plasticizing
367 effect of PEO enhances chain mobility of PLA, while TGA confirmed the addition of PEO
368 increased the thermal stability of PLA. Moreover, the surface wettability and flexibility of PLA
369 were improved by blending PLA with PEO. According to surface morphology, the film surface
370 of the 3:1 PLA/PEO blend was more porous, which resulted in the creation of easier diffusion
371 pathways for oxygen and water vapor. A similar finding has also been observed in a study
372 involving three mixtures of PLA/PEO blends (3:1, 1:1 and 1:3). A 3:1 ratio of the solution blend
373 of PLA/PEO was found to be the most homogenous and best in terms of its miscibility [Oliveira
374 *et al.*, 2013].
375

376
377 **Figure 3.** SEM images, (a) neat PLA film ($\times 4000$); (b) 3:1 PLA/PEO blended film ($\times 4000$),
378 Microscopic images, (c) 3D substrate of 3:1 PLA/PEO blend ($\times 200$); (d) 3D substrate coated
379 with CoCl_2 and EDX analysis (e) uncoated 3D substrate and (f) 3D substrate coated with CoCl_2 .

380
381

382 **Table 5.** Chemical composition on the surface of polymer blended 3D substrate.

Sample	Chemical composition (% Weight)			
	C	O	Co	Cl
Uncoated	48.85	51.15	-	-
Coated by 4 layers of CoCl ₂	55.99	26.27	6.52	11.22

383

384 **3.2 Color observation**385 **3.2.1 Colorimetric humidity sensors through printing technology**

386 In accordance with the positive points mentioned above, the 3:1 PLA/PEO blend was also
387 fabricated as a solvent-cast by 3D printing to establish a 3D substrate. The 3D substrate was
388 designed in spherical and square shapes, as shown in Figure 4(a). The main parameters in this
389 work included applied pressure, printing speed, nozzle diameter (Gauge size) and a concentration
390 of the 3:1 PLA/PEO blended solution. The suitable applied pressure and printing speed were
391 within the range of 3-4.5 bars and 25-30 mm/s, respectively. The studied concentrations of the
392 polymer solution were 20, 30 and 40 %w/v. To fabricate a 3D structure, a smaller nozzle
393 diameter is required for faster solvent evaporation and a higher degree of viscosity of the
394 solution. High concentrations of the solutions, increased printing speeds, reduced nozzle diameter
395 or a reduction in the applied pressure enabled faster solvent evaporation rates to rapidly enhance
396 the rigidity of the 3D structure in order for it to support itself after extrusion [Guo *et al.*, 2014].
397 Thus, the solvent evaporation rate and viscosity of the solution must be suitable for effective
398 fabrication. In addition, adequate viscosity of the solution is required to allow oxygen and water
399 vapor to flow easily through the nozzle and to achieve a smooth filament [Guo *et al.*, 2014]. A 40
400 %w/v solution was not effectively fabricated because it was not able to flow smoothly through
401 the nozzle with a degree of high viscosity. A 20 %w/v solution was unable to flow continuously
402 through the nozzle as the viscosity was too low and it did not exhibit enough rigidity to support
403 itself after extrusion [Guo *et al.*, 2013; Guo *et al.*, 2014]. Notably, the 30 %w/v of 3:1 PLA/PEO
404 blend solution successfully fabricated the 3D substrate. Four layers at a thickness of ~ 0.3 mm,
405 with square-shaped areas of 5 cm × 5 cm and spherical shapes that were 5 cm in diameter of the
406 3D substrates were fabricated before being coated with the CoCl₂ solution by inkjet printing.

407 The CoCl₂ solution that was used as ink was successfully prepared by dissolving 50 wt% of
408 CoCl₂ in DMF solvent and then printed by inkjet onto the 3D substrate of the 3:1 PLA/PEO
409 blends. The solution had particles that were below 0.30 μm pore size of the fluids using a 0.30
410 μm syringe filter. The 4×4 cm square-shaped areas of the CoCl₂ solution with the four-layered
411 materials were printed on the 3D substrates, EDX spectrum confirmed that the relevant elements,
412 including Co, Cl, O and C, were coated onto the surface of the 3D substrate.

413

414 **3.2.2 RGB analysis**

415 For the detection of humidity, the RGB value was used to confirm the color changes
416 [Bridgeman, Corral, Quach, Xian, Forzani, 2014; Hirayama, Takayama, Haruta, Ishibashi,
417 Takeuchi, 2017] of the colorimetric humidity sensors via “Adobe Photoshop”. With higher levels
418 of humidity, the photographs of the samples appeared to become more concentrated as the color

419 changed from pink from blue. The red and blue value changes of the samples at various relative
 420 humidity levels (12-100 %RH) indicated that the colorimetric humidity sensors could be used to
 421 determine the presence of moisture in the surrounding environment. Above 60%RH, the red
 422 value was significantly increased along with an increase in relative humidity from 3.5 to 151.2 at
 423 68%RH, as is shown in Figure 4(b)-(c). As can be seen in the photographs, when these
 424 colorimetric humidity sensors were exposed to relative levels of humidity, the color changed
 425 from blue at low relative humidity levels (12-60 %RH) to pink at high relative humidity levels
 426 (above 60%RH). Remarkably, the RGB results corresponded to the photographs of the samples
 427 when exposed to different humidity levels.
 428

429 **Figure 4.** Materials color observation; a) Photographs of 3D substrates in square-shape,
 430 cylindrical-shape and coated with the CoCl_2 solution applied by inkjet printing, respectively; b)
 431 photograph of color changes during the test of the sensors (blue to pink); c) RGB analysis of
 432 photographs of colorimetric humidity sensors when exposed to different levels of humidity.
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 434

435 As is evident in Figure 4(b), this reaction is a hydration reaction with CoCl_2 absorbing
 436 water. As the humidity increases two water molecules surround each cobalt atom. Subsequently,
 437 cobalt chloride dihydrate is formed as shown in equation (2) and the color purple is observed. As
 438 the humidity increases further, the crystal structure of the cobalt chloride rearranges itself to

439 allow four more water molecules to surround each cobalt atom. The cobalt chloride hexahydrate
440 is subsequently formed as shown in equation (3) and a pink color observed [Tsigara *et al.*, 2017,
441 You *et al.*, 2017].

442

445

446 **3.2.3 Repeatability**

447 The response and recovery behavior of the colorimetric humidity sensors are important
448 properties for the accuracy of these sensors. The time taken for the color changes were tested by
449 alternating the sensors between closed containers at either high humidity levels (68-96% RH) or
450 low humidity levels (21% RH), respectively for 5 cycles. This was carried out for 3 conditions
451 which correspond to 21-68% RH, 21-75% RH and 21-96% RH. The dip-coated polymer blended
452 films with 50% CoCl₂ solution, dipped for various times (1, 3, and 5 minutes), were compared
453 with the 3D coated polymer blend with the 50% CoCl₂ solution applied by inkjet printing. Figure
454 5 presents the response and recovery times of the colorimetric humidity sensors that were used to
455 evaluate the accuracy of these sensors [You *et al.*, 2017]. The results of these three conditions
456 indicate that the response time of each sample was influenced by the humidity conditions, while
457 each cycle displayed a similar saw-tooth shape. For humidity sensing, the PLA/PEO blended
458 substrates coated with 50% CoCl₂ exhibited good repeatability behavior at different humidity
459 levels. Furthermore, the sensitivity of these sensors differed after different coating techniques
460 were used, wherein the four-layer inkjet-coating sensors at the highest humidity level yielded
461 overall color changes of less than 50 minutes (black solid line) when compared to the dip-coated
462 sensors. On the other hand, the sensitivity of the inkjet-coated sensors was higher or similar to
463 that of the dip-coating sensors at 96%RH (highest humidity). This would suggest that the amount
464 of the colorimetric sensing solution affects the sensitivity of the sensors in accordance with a
465 small (picolitre) drop volume of the inkjet coating method.
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Figure 5. RGB analysis of photographs of colorimetric humidity sensors when exposed to different humidity levels: a) 68% RH; b) 75% RH; c) 96% RH.

3.2.4 Total color difference (TCD)

Total color difference (TCD) was studied to determine the sensitivity of the color changes of the colorimetric humidity sensors at different times. The samples obtained under different humidity levels were indicated by lightness (L^*), green color (a^*), yellow color (b^*) and total color difference (ΔE) between the final and initial labels, respectively [Díaz et al., 2016; Díaz et al., 2019]. Furthermore, %RH significantly affected the color changes at various times. At 96%RH, the humidity sensors appeared to become gradually brighter with time ($L^* > 0$), redder ($a^* > 0$) and less blue ($b^* > 0$). Color changes of the CoCl_2 humidity indicator were observed at the a^* and b^* values. As is evident from Table 6 and Figure 6, a^* , b^* and ΔE tended to increase over time as compared to the initial color of the humidity sensors at 96 %RH (the highest %RH value). These results are consistent with the RGB results. As the sensitivity at the highest %RH of these sensors, TCD initiated an increase within 5 minutes and clearly changed color at 40 minutes.

485

486 **Figure 6.** TCD for color change of the colorimetric humidity sensors at different times; a) a^* ; b)

487 b^* at highest 96%RH; c) ΔE of the color change and d) CIELAB color chart.

488

489 **Table 6.** Total color difference of colorimetric humidity sensors at the highest %RH (96%).

Time (min)	L^*	a^*	b^*	ΔE
0 Initial sample (Blue color)	74.81	-22.82	-18.03	0
5	68.66	-16.80	-11.50	10.80
10	56.91	-10.29	-6.24	24.83
15	59.42	-9.77	-5.24	23.90
20	62.85	-6.17	-2.60	25.66
30	67.21	-3.13	-0.17	27.65
40	75.26	0.06	2.38	30.66
50 Final sample (Pink color)	84.15	6.77	5.70	39.06

490

491 4. Conclusions

492 To enhance the poor thermal properties of PLA, along with its low flexibility and poor
 493 hydrophilicity, a preparation of PLA was successfully melt-blended at 180 °C for 8 minutes with
 494 PEO at a ratio of 3:1 PLA/PEO. The flexibility of the PLA/PEO blend increased with the addition
 495 of PEO. The hydrophilicity of the 3:1 PLA/PEO blend and the thermal stability of PLA were

496 found to be enhanced when compared with neat PLA. The morphology of the polymer blends
497 indicated the establishment of good substrate properties. This was the result of a more porous
498 structure spread throughout the surface which resulted in inferior barrier properties. A 30 %w/v
499 of the PLA/PEO blend solution in chloroform solvent was used to fabricate the 3D substrate by
500 3D printing. This approach was then used to create a custom-made environmentally friendly
501 colorimetric humidity sensor. For the coating step, inkjet printing technology was used to coat a
502 CoCl₂ solution onto the 3D polymer substrate with the use of a commercial inkjet material
503 printer. The optimal ink for the colorimetric humidity indicator was prepared from 50 %w/v
504 CoCl₂ in the DMF solvent. The colorimetric humidity sensors clearly exhibited different colors
505 within 40 minutes over the range of 60-100 %RH. This outcome indicated that the 3D substrate
506 coated with CoCl₂ has promising potential for applications in product humidity monitoring.
507 Moreover, the advantages of this technology, such as high-frequency continuous operation, small
508 volumes and highly controlled ink-drop patterning, can be applied to other polymers for
509 alternative novel innovations using environmentally friendly materials.

510

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